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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Heavy Ion SEE Testing Power Electronics for the Satellite ROMEO (HI-SEE-ROMEO V2)</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA09-299</i>
General application	<i>Space, Small Satellites, CubeSats</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Thorben Loeffler, Institute of Space Systems at University of Stuttgart</i>
Author list	<i>Jonas Burgdorf Institute of Space Systems at University of Stuttgart Kevin Waizenegger Institute of Space Systems at University of Stuttgart</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>03/19/24 – 03/22/24</i>
Facility	<i>UCL Universite Catholique de Louvain Heavy Ion Irradiation Facility (HIF)</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>24 h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The exploration of harsh radiation environments in space presents significant challenges for satellite missions, particularly in terms of component reliability and cost-effectiveness. This study aims to contribute to the development of cost-efficient research satellite missions by focusing on the identification and qualification of suitable radiation-tolerant commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) power electronics. Following devices were tested: EPC2014C (GaN FET) EPC, FPF2700 (OCP high load switch) Fairchild Semiconductor, and TPS2553DRVR-1 (OCP low load switch) Texas Instruments.

The selected components will be applied as protection function in the power subsystem of the University Stuttgart small satellite mission Research and Observation in Medium Earth Orbit (ROMEO), with the incentive to maximize the reliability of the spacecraft and the scientific payloads, and therefore increase the success of the mission goals. The operation of a radiation tolerant platform in MEO shall be demonstrated. The scientific objectives of the ROMEO mission are climate research, space weather research as well as the qualification of a water-based propulsion system. The development overview is published throughout the phases A [1-1] B [1-2] and C [1-3].

The test and beam requirements are mainly designed according to the ESCC Basic Specification 25100 [1-4], but with state-of-the-art methods to decrease the necessary beam time according to the CNES "Proposal of a Lightened Radiation Hardness Assurance Methodology for New Space" [1-5].

Therefore, the main goal of the test campaign is to gain insight in the radiation tolerance of the components while minimizing the necessary beam time.

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The essential difference to the ESCC-25100 is that the samples are tested for a minimum of two energy levels in the LET-spectrum, instead of five. While this can make it difficult to obtain a Weibull-Fit for the cross-section analysis, it is enough for a practical pass/fail-verdict for usage in a space environment.

Experiment test report

The experimental report describes the test procedure with its verification approach, the test setup, devices under test (DUTs) information, and test conditions. The test results are analysed by applying the insights to the modelled ROMEO mission particle fluence. A basic prediction of the expected upset rate for the one-year mission concludes the research.

Pass/Fail approach:

First a test with a high LET of 40 MeV/cm²/mg (fluence of 10⁷ ions/cm²) has to be conducted. If the samples do not pass this first test, a consecutive test inducing a medium LET of 15 MeV/cm²/mg will be performed. For evaluation, components resisting a high LET will be considered low risk and can be implemented in critical satellite functions. Components which only resist the medium LET requirements should only be used for uncritical applications on the satellite. As the occurrence of radiation induced failure modes like Single Event Upsets (SEU) and Single Event Latchups (SEL) is a stochastic event, the results of the tests paired with the radiation analysis of the dedicated orbit, a confidence level can be calculated for the components.

In order to achieve the desired sample size, 4 similar DUTs are tested parallelly.

Test setup:

The test series consists of three power components, with a sample size of four for each type, resulting in a total of twelve DUTs. These devices require a similar test setup with logic control to enable the devices and a resistive/capacitive load to simulate the operational conditions. Further, each device is connected to a current-sensing and over-current protection circuit to enable latch-up monitoring of the DUTs. The reset time of a component following an over-current state takes around 2s.

The test setup depicted in

Figure 1 is designed to be modular, only requiring the swapping of the DUT PCBs between tests. The DUT PCBs connect to a peripheral electronics PCB which can support all four samples in parallel. This PCB includes current and voltage monitoring, adjustable latch-up control for the DUTs and interfaces to external power supplies. The peripheral electronics are controlled by a raspberry pi single board computer. An additional load can be switched to each channel in order to simulate over-current events for the DUTs.

Figure 1: Schematic of the test setup to detect SEE

General test conditions:

Test conditions are maximum operating conditions on the satellite system. The absolute maximum ratings of the components can differ and are not part of the testing procedure. The tests are performed in a vacuum-chamber with an ambient pressure of 1.2E-4 mPa. All four samples of the DUT are positioned to be in the beamline for parallel irradiation.

The DUTs are temperature controlled by an external controller using resistive heaters, which are installed next to each device, as well as temperature sensors for the feedback loop.

Verification requirements:

During irradiation, the test setup tries to reset the DUTs if they experience a latch-up. If more than one sample is not resettable after a latch-up, a destructive failure is assumed, which renders the DUT failed for the target LET. The component passes the verification, if the component resumes to nominal conditions after such an event. These so-called transient events only harm the operations of a satellite, if the off-time is significant impairing its duty cycle.

If the total fluence is reached without a destructive event, or at least three out of four devices are still functional, the tests can be proceeded in run number order. Some devices have different operational conditions to be tested in. If two or more DUTs are compromised by destructive events, the DUTs shall be changed and tests proceed with reduced Target LET.

Sampling of test data:

Following parameters are sampled with 300 Hz for all parallelly irradiated DUTs: Input- and Output-Voltage, Output-Current, and Temperature. The date is stored on a microcontroller for further analysis.

DUTs description and irradiation Results:

Following devices were tested: EPC2014C (GaN FET) EPC, FPF2700 (OCP high load switch) Fairchild Semiconductor, and TPS2553DRVR-1 (OCP low load switch) Texas Instruments.

Table 1 summarizes the test results of the three DUTs. Each test session categorizes tests with the same device and same particle. Ideally each device should be tested for up to four different modes, but if one mode failed, further testing is cancelled. For a device to pass, all modes should be successfully tested for each energy level.

Table 1: Test sessions, Beam parameter and Results of the test campaign.

Test session	No. of tests	Device	Test conditions	Particle	Energy [MeV]	LET [MeV cm ² /mg]	Flux [/s /cm ²]	Fluence [/cm ²]	Destructive Events	Transient Events [Max.]	Verification
1	2	EPC2014C	1.4A@8V, T=60°C	Xe	995	62.5	8e3	1e7	yes	-	Failed
2	1	EPC2014C	1.4A@8V, T=60°C	Cr	505	16.1	-	-	inconclusive	-	inconclusive
3	1	FPF2700	1.9A@33.6V, T=80°C	Xe	995	62.5	1e3	1e6	yes	-	Failed
4	2	FPF2700	1.9A@33.6V, T=80°C	Cr	505	16.1	3e2	2e5	yes	-	Failed
5	4	TPS2553	0.2A@5V, T=80°C	Xe	995	62.5	8e3	1e7	no	493	Passed
6	4	TPS2553	0.2A@5V, T=80°C	Rh	957	46.1	8e3	1e7	no	469	Passed
7	4	TPS2553	0.2A@5V, T=80°C	Cr	505	16.1	8e3	1e7	no	161	Passed
8	4	TPS2553	0.2A@5V, T=80°C	Al	250	5.7	8e3	1e7	no	34	Passed

Test reports:

Test Report: Radiation Effects on GaNFET EPC2014C

The test subject was the EPC2014C, a Gallium Nitride Field-Effect Transistor (GaN FET) manufactured by Efficient Power Conversion Corporation, Inc. This device is supplied in passivated die form and features a 40V drain-source voltage rating with a 10A continuous drain current capability.

The device was not delidded due to its passivated die form. To access the sensitive area, an inverse mounting technique, commonly known as "Dead-Bugging," was employed. This method involves flipping the device upside down for testing purposes.

1. Xenon Particle Irradiation (Xe995)
 - The devices were exposed to Xe995.
 - Result: Destructive events occurred within seconds of exposure.

- Outcome: All DUTs failed and could not be reset, resulting in test failure.
2. Chromium Particle Irradiation (Cr505)
 - Scheduled test could not be conducted.
 - Reason: Thermal issues arose during preparation, likely due to the inverse mounting technique.

The inverse mounting method (Dead-Bugging) employed to access the sensitive area of the GaNFET introduced significant thermal management challenges. These thermal issues prevented the execution of the planned Cr505 irradiation test.

The test results are deemed inconclusive due to the following factors. First, rapid failure of devices during Xenon particle irradiation and second, the inability to conduct Chromium particle irradiation due to thermal complications.

To obtain more conclusive results, it is recommended that a specified heat sink be installed to address the thermal issues encountered during inverse mounting in vacuum.

Test Report: Radiation Effects on OCP High Load Switch FPF2700

The test subject was the FPF2700, an Over-Current Protection (OCP) high load switch, packaged in SOP8, and manufactured by Semiconductor Components Industries, LLC. This device is designed for high-current load switching applications.

The casings of the FPF2700 devices were decapsulated using laser ablation and chemical processes to facilitate detailed analysis.

1. Xenon Particle Irradiation (Xe995)
 - The devices were exposed to Xe995.
 - Result: Destructive failure occurred on all devices.
2. Chromium Particle Irradiation (Cr505)
 - The devices were exposed to Cr505.
 - Result: Destructive failure occurred on all devices.

The FPF2700 demonstrated high susceptibility to destructive SEL under both Xenon and Chromium particle irradiation. The inability to reset any of the devices after exposure indicates a severe vulnerability to radiation-induced effects.

Given the high susceptibility to destructive SEL, it is not recommended to use the FPF2700 in harsh radiation environments.

Test Report: Radiation Effects on OCP Low Load Switch TPS2553

The test subject was the TPS2553, an Over-Current Protection (OCP) low load switch, packaged in WSON6 2x2, and manufactured by Texas Instruments Incorporated. This device is designed to provide precision adjustable current-limited power switching.

The casings of the TPS2553 devices were decapsulated using laser ablation and chemical processes to uncover the sensitive area. Due to rapid failure in the previous tests, the sequence was modified to maximize the remaining beam time for in-depth analysis. Initial tests were conducted using lower LET Aluminium particles (AL250) to minimize potential immediate destructive latch-ups.

1. Aluminium Particle Irradiation (AL250)
 - The device was successfully tested under nominal conditions.
 - Subsequently, the device mode was set to Over-Current State with decreased fluence to

- observe responses in alternative operational modes.
- Devices were also tested in Off-State to analyse leakage current and voltage spike occurrences.
 - The device successfully passed AL250 irradiation without destructive events, confirming successful verification. 24 - 34 transient events, which were resettable occurred.
2. Chromium Particle Irradiation (Cr505),
 - Same procedure was repeated for Cr505.
 - The device successfully passed Cr505 irradiation without destructive events, confirming successful verification. 145-161 transient events, which were resettable occurred.
 3. Rhodium Particle Irradiation (Rh957),
 - The same procedure was repeated for Rh957.
 - The device successfully passed Rh957 irradiation without destructive events, confirming successful verification. 452-469 transient events, which were resettable occurred.
 4. Xenon Particle Irradiation (Xe995),
 - The same procedure was repeated for Xe995.
 - The device successfully passed Xe995 irradiation without destructive events, confirming successful verification. 465-493 transient events, which were resettable occurred.

The TPS2553 demonstrated resilience against destructive latch-ups across various particle irradiations. Although no destructive latch-ups were observed, transient events ranging from 24 to 493 were recorded. This sensitivity should be mitigated by reset-functions in the application circuit. *Figure 2* illustrates the resulting latch-up cross-section of the device using a weibull-fit on the test datapoints.

Figure 2: Weibull Fit of the Latch-Up cross section of four data points of the TPS2553.

Upset Rate Calculation:

Utilizing ESA’s Space Environment Information System (SPENVIS), the average ion integral flux was simulated with following relevant settings: Trapped Protons, AP8, Solar Minimum, Solar Particle Peak Fluxes (Worst-Day), Creme96 H->U, Galactic Cosmic Ray Fluxes, H->U, ISO15930 Standard Model.

Figure 3: Integral Flux (4pi) vs. LET spectrum of the one-year ROMEO Mission in a 330x2500km orbit with an inclination of 96.7° and a perigee drift of 2.3°/day.

Both, the worst-case and average integral flux are simulated and compared. The difference can be up to two magnitudes higher in worst-case conditions. Using the cross-section data from testing, a latch-up rate of 0.05 to 2.5 upsets per year per device can be noted. Using almost 100 similar devices on the satellite leads to certain latch-up conditions. Therefore, the possibility to power-cycle the devices must be implemented. Since the devices demonstrated normal operation following each latch-up occurrence, these failure modes are generally considered non-critical for satellite operations.

Conclusion:

The objective of finding suitable power electronics for harsh radiation environments was successful in many aspects. Additionally, the experimental testing offered insights into how to improve for further test campaigns. Mostly, the thermal integration of the DUTs must be prioritized as the decapsulating process, or dead-bugging method can greatly increase the risk of thermal damage to the devices during operations.

As for the device qualification: Out of three unique devices, one has passed the requirements to be used as satellite hardware. While the FPF2700 and the EPC2014C experienced destructive failures, the TPS2553 could be reset to its nominal function after any latch-up event.

The device was tested up to LET of 62.5 MeV by Xenon particles and received a TID of more than 20 krad, but did not show any signs of degradation for its intended purpose after annealing.

However, up to 493 latch-up events were registered at the highest particle energy. Therefore, it is recommended to apply the component in a circuit with reset feature, in case the component experiences a transient SEL in orbit. Combining the gathered cross-section data with the modelled particle fluence data in orbit, a latch-up frequency of up to 2.5 upsets per year per device can be expected. From a reliability point-of-view this is rare enough to not compromise valuable operations time, but frequent enough that the failure mode must be mitigated.

References:

- 1-1 Löffler, T., Burgdorf, J., Hildebrandt, J., Bötsch-Zavřel, L., Pätschke, S., Petri, J., Kuhm, H., Lengowski, M. and Klinkner, S., 2021. Research and Observation in Medium Earth Orbit (ROMEEO) with a cost effective micro satellite platform. In 72nd International Astronautical Congress (IAC), Dubai.
- 1-2 Löffler, T., Burgdorf, J., Hildebrandt, J., Bötsch-Zavřel, L., Holeczek, C., Pätschke, S., Kanzow, M., Largent, P., Petri, J., Lengowski, M. and Klinkner, S., 2022. Preliminary Design of the Radiation Protection of the ROMEEO Satellite in the lower Medium Earth Orbit. In 73rd International Astronautical Congress..
- 1-3 Waizenegger K., Löffler, T., Burgdorf, J., Acker, D., Bötsch-Zavrel, L., Eggert, M., Hildebrandt, J., Holeczek, C., Kanzow, M., Konieczny, D., Mohr, U., Nehlich, P., Schweigert, R., Starzmann, D., Steinert, M., Vikas, A., Vossoughi, B., Zink, J., Lengowski, M. and Klinkner, S., 2024. System Design Phase C of the Satellite ROMEEO for the Inner Radiation Belt of the Medium Earth Orbi. In 75th International Astronautical Congress (IAC), Milan, Italy.
- 1-4 ESA, "Single Event Effects Test Method and Guidelines, ESCC Basic Specification No. 25100", (2014).
- 1-5 Bezerra, F., Mekki, J., Augustin, G., Guillermin, J. and Chatry, N., 2021, September. Proposal of a lightened radiation hardness assurance methodology for new space. In 2021 21th European Conference on Radiation and Its Effects on Components and Systems (RADECS) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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